

Educational Resource Management through IOT

Mr. Shrinath S. Pai

Research Scholar, Jain University, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

Dr. J Meenakumari, Professor, Alliance University, Bangalore

Abstract:

“The Internet of Things is a technology which is widely expanding its application area to cater the diverse needs of organizations. It allows people and objects to be connected Anytime, Anywhere, preferably by means of Any path/network and Any service.” In this article there is a brief overview of IoT application areas, need for resource management in Education sector“. The article consists of three main parts: first, an overview of IoT applications, second, Resource Management in Educational Institution and third IoT Implementation ideas.

Keyword : - IoT Application, Resource Management, IOT Reference Model, Current Technology

Introduction

Whether you call it the “Internet of Things,” the “Internet of Everything,” the “Connected World,” “IoT” or just plain amazing, the rapidly expanding thread of connectivity among everyday objects via the internet is changing how the world works. The IoT connects everyday objects to the internet, saving consumers time and money, driving economic growth. [1]

Internet of Things (IoT) environment consists of a lot of small devices that sense and gather information from their turbulent environment. The gathered data are transmitted to the sink node that these data are analyzed such as cloud. IoT environment pose many challenges because of device energy limitation, low computational power, low memory, unattended operation, and dynamic environmental changes. [2]

In spite of its various challenges, the IoT is used in many areas. Out of all application areas education sector too has wide application. Every educational institution consists of various types of resources. If the resources in educational institutions are managed successfully, then it leads to the successful management of the institution. These institutions rely on various internet enabled mobile devices. If the effective communication is achieved between these, in turn it leads to the successful overall governance of the institution.

In this paper, we are focused on educational resource management. Listing of application areas, types of resources required, IoT enabled solution is discussed here.

Characteristics of IoT: [3]

- **Interconnectivity:** With regard to the IoT, anything can be interconnected with the global information and communication infrastructure.
- **Things-related services:** The IoT is capable of providing thing-related services within the constraints of things, such as privacy protection and semantic consistency between physical things and their associated virtual things. In order to provide thing-related services within the constraints of things, both the technologies in physical world and information world will change.
- **Heterogeneity:** The devices in the IoT are heterogeneous as based on different hardware platforms and networks. They can interact with other devices or service platforms through different networks.
- **Dynamic changes:** The state of devices change dynamically, e.g., sleeping and waking up, connected and/or disconnected as well as the context of devices including location and speed. Moreover, the number of devices can change dynamically.
- **Enormous scale:** The number of devices that need to be managed and that communicate with each other will be at least an order of magnitude larger than the devices connected to the current Internet. Even more critical will be the management of the data generated and their interpretation for application purposes. This relates to semantics of data, as well as efficient data handling.
- **Safety:** As we gain benefits from the IoT, we must not forget about safety. As both the creators and recipients of the IoT, we must design for safety. This includes the safety of our personal data and the safety of our physical well-being. Securing the endpoints, the networks, and the data moving across all of it means creating a security paradigm that will scale.
- **Connectivity:** Connectivity enables network accessibility and compatibility. Accessibility is getting on a network while compatibility provides the common ability to consume and produce data.

IoT Application Areas

In education sector, there are lots of sub areas which use the diversified resources. To manage and maintain these resources, the organization is depending on technology. The technology enabled resource management system is highly appreciated because of various unique reasons. The next level of resource management can be thought of, by the use of IoT enabled technology.

IoT Systems is used in following areas of educational organization for the effective resource management.

- **Attendance Management [4]**

Attendance is for keeping records of number of students, employees present in Institution.

Complexity of this process increases even more with increase in number of Human Resource.

This can be done using two hardware devices.

1. Handheld device (for taking attendance) designed on Adrino microcontroller, LCD, Zig-Bee module, Fingerprint module.
2. Local server (Raspberry Pi)

- **Campus Energy Management & Eco-system Management [5]**

Internet of things has been applied in energy management and Eco-system monitoring to provide energy efficiency for a much more sustainable future. This has resulted in the introduction of Smart Grid, a specific form of IoT energy management application, by several national governments .The utility companies can effectively balance power generation and energy usage to provide more efficient operations by adding intelligence to the existing infrastructure. Through the use of specialized sensors and actuator systems, energy consumption information will be gathered automatically to improve economy, efficiency and reliability of the systems.

- **Secured Classroom and Campus System [6]**

As educational organizations begin to leverage solutions like cloud computing and radio frequency identification (RFID) across an IoT platform, they're able to capture, manage and analyze Big Data. This insight provides stakeholders with a real-time view of students, staff and assets. It is this asset intelligence that enables institutions to make more informed decisions in an effort to improve student learning experiences, operational efficiency and campus security.

- **Smart Campus Management [7]**

Intelligent campus (i-campus) refers to a holistic intelligent campus environment, in which initiatives such as cloud and mobile-powered learning, RFID-based security management are established to support holistic e-learning, networking, and governance.

The traditional way of delivering Massive Open Online Courses could limit a learner's learning experience, especially when appreciating some tacit knowledge such as a unique culture and a roomy environment. The authors came up with smart phone enabled virtual reality educational content that can create immersive and better learning experience for online learners.

- **Water Resource monitoring and management [8]**

Water resource information on-line monitoring is basic and important to water resource management. The integrated system based on internet of things (IoT) for water resources monitoring and management consists of three key layers: equipment perception layer, information transmission layer and data application layer. In equipment perception layer, Sensor network for monitoring water information is constructed. In information transmission layer, real-time information transmission is achieved. In data application layer, water information are stored, managed, applied and shared on internet by users. Application shows that the system can provide real time and reliable water resource information for water resource management.

- **Green Campus [9]**

G-IoT takes advantage over IoT in order to add additional benefits to the educational sector -economically, socially and environmentally sustainability. Following G-IoT practices, the usage of facilities becomes more efficient through minimizing energy and other resources consumption. This lead to preserving natural resources, minimal or no impact of the technology on the environment and human health and significant cost reduction. From the G-IoT involvement in the education sector, all participants will benefit, student and teachers will improve their activities in safe and secure educational environment, while management, organizational structures, and a government will achieve significant financial savings what will significantly contribute to sustainable development of whole education sector.

- **Learning [10]**

Application of IoT in education opens up opportunities for learning. Hence it enables learners to access, extend, transform and share ideas and information in multi-modal communication styles and format. Some of the benefits of IoT includes improving learning skills, enhances mobile learning, helps in easy data collection and analysis.

- **Smart Transportation [11]**

The transportation facility of the school can be upgraded with the use of IoT. It leads to the effective management of vehicles, schedule and other relevant attributes.

- **Printing Management [12]**

Self-service technology (SST) is a technical platform which allow users to independently produce their required services without any service personal. Self-service print technology (SSTP) provides an efficient solution to intelligitized administration management. By incorporating the IoT Technology we can administer the Printing equipments.

Need for Resource Management [13]

The IoT is a relation between real world and virtual world. IoT are millions of smart object connected to internet. In resource management are managing these millions of object in single application.

There is various issues related to resource management in IoT.

1. The need for resource management is a real time network monitoring and control network.
2. Real time fault reporting is an important characteristic of resource management.
3. Detecting the possible anomaly is an important point for the IoT resource management to ensure the reliability of the data.
4. Increasing the smartness of nodes to increase the efficiency of the constrained networks.
5. To decrease the power consumption.
6. To track the all devices connected to internet.

The main goal of resource management is better utilize of the open resources and raising the Qos (quality of the services) accessible to the people, while reducing the expenses of the public administration.

Key Activities for Resource Management in IoT [14]

In order to describe the core activities of a generic framework for resource management in IoT, we consider a hypothetical model for an IoT ecosystem with either three or two tiers (Fig. 2.2), in which:

- (i) the bottom tier encompasses the things (IoT devices/nodes/smart objects)
- (ii) the top tier encompasses cloud nodes and
- (iii) an optional middle tier consists in Smart Gateways or edge nodes.

Resource Modeling

The first issue about the resource management process is how applications and resource management systems describe resources in an IoT ecosystem. The resource model is a vital part of any RML since it defines the entities, properties and relationships that build up the system, thus driving the whole operation of the resource manager.

Resource Allocation

The final goal of the resource allocation activity, which is the responsibility of a resource allocation system (RAS) within the RML, is to properly accommodate the workload of all the applications currently using the IoT system, by allocating the required (virtual or physical) resources so that expected outcomes of all the applications are provided and the QoS requirements are met.

Fig. 1 Activities involved in the resource management

Resource Discovery

Before the necessary resources can be allocated, they need to be discovered in the IoT ecosystem. Resource discovery in such a heterogeneous system is in itself a challenge, worsened by the current lack of standardization of protocols and formats in the field.

Resource Monitoring

Another activity that is necessary so that a RMS tackles the highly dynamic nature of IoT systems is resource monitoring. The execution environment is extremely dynamic, including variations related to the user, the network, the physical environment and the devices. The monitoring of these environmental variations is essential to provide a high-quality service.

Resource Estimation

Sometimes it is useful trying to estimate the amount of resources to be used to better assure the successful completion of the application. Strategies for resource estimation are usually based on keeping historical data of the consumption.

Architectural Reference Model

Starting with existing architectures and solutions, generic baseline requirements can be extracted and used as an input to the design. The IoT-A ARM

It consists of four parts:

Starting with existing architectures and solutions, generic baseline requirements can be extracted and used as an input to the design.

Figure 2: IoT-A architectural reference model building blocks.

The IoT-A ARM consists of four parts: [15]

The vision:

It summarises the rationale for providing an architectural reference model for the IoT. At the same time it discusses underlying assumptions, such as motivations. It also discusses

how the architectural reference model can be used, the methodology applied to the architecture modeling, and the business scenarios and stakeholders addressed.

Business scenarios:

Business scenarios defined as requirements by stakeholders are the drivers of the architecture work. With the knowledge of businesses aspirations, a holistic view of IoT architectures can be derived. Furthermore, a concrete instance of the reference architecture can be validated against selected business scenarios. A stakeholder analysis contributes to understanding which aspects of the architectural reference model need to be described for the different stakeholders and their concerns. According to common usage, this part constitutes a subset of the vision.

The IoT Reference Model

The IoT Reference Model provides the highest abstraction level for the definition of the IoT-A Architectural Reference Model. It promotes a common understanding of the IoT domain. The description of the IoT Reference Model includes a general discourse on the IoT domain, an IoT Domain Model as a top-level description, an IoT Information Model explaining how IoT information is going to be modelled, and an IoT Communication Model in order to understand specifics about communication between many heterogeneous IoT devices and the Internet as a whole. The definition of the IoT Reference Model is conforming to the OASIS reference model definition

IoT Reference Architecture

The IoT Reference Architecture is the reference for building compliant IoT architectures. As such, it provides views and perspectives on different architectural aspects that are of concern to stakeholders of the IoT. The terms view and perspectives are used according to the general literature and standards. The creation of the IoT Reference Architecture focuses on abstract sets of mechanisms rather than concrete application architectures

Conclusion

This paper describes how the Internet of Things (IoT) can shape the educational institutions. The educational institutions are totally rely on the divergent resources and the management of these resources effectively will help the organization to prosper through various means. The IoT Technology can be used in various sectors of educational unit and the transformation can be seen.

REFERENCES

- [1] INTERNET OF THINGS:.,A Framework for the Next Administration, November 2016, Consumer Technology Association
- [2] D Lee, H Lee, K Yim, "Proxy based Resource Management Scheme in IoT Environment", 10th International Conference on Broadband and Wireless Computing, Communication and Applications,2015
- [3] K Patel,S Patel, "Internet of Things-IOT: Definition, Characteristics, Architecture, Enabling Technologies, Application & Future Challenges", ,IJESC ISSN 2321 3361,Volume 6 Issue No. 5, 2016
- [4] D.Narendharsingh, A Reddy, S Sudhir, IOT BASED WIRELESS ATTENDANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM USING FINGER PRINT RECOGNITION, ,International Journal of Latest Trends in Engineering and Technology, e-ISSN:2278-621X, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21172/1.73.554>, Vol.(7)Issue(3), pp. 410-418
- [5] BAGHERI, Maryam and HAGHIGHI MOVAHED, Siavosh, The Effect of the Internet of Things (IoT) on Education Business Model ,<http://shura.shu.ac.uk/14405>
- [6] Zebra Technologies, "How the Internet of Things Is Transforming Education"
- [7] SUTD Library Special Alerts, Smart Campus, December 2016
- [8] Mo Xiaocong, Qiu Xin Jiao,Shen Shaohong, "An IoT-based system for water resources monitoring and management", 7th International Conference on Intelligent Human-Machine Systems and Cybernetics,2015
- [9] M Maksimović, "TRANSFORMING EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT THROUGH GREEN INTERNET OF THINGS (G-IOT)",2017.32, Paper No.T1.1-3
- [10] Osisanwo, F.Y, Izang, A.A, Kuyoro, S. O, & John, Henry Chukwudi, "Internet of Things (IOTs) Bridging the Gap in Tertiary Educational Process", International Journal of Computer Trends and Technology (IJCTT) – Volume 42 Number 2 – December 2016
- [11] SE Water Avenue Suite, Portland, Oregon 97214,248–4300,clarity-innovations.com
- [12] Xu Ziqian, Sha Li,Yu Shuyi,"Design and Implementation of an expandable SSTP system for educational administration",Eighth International Conference on Measuring Technology and Mechatronics Automation,2016
- [13] D Jadhav, S Nikam,"Need for Resource Management in IoT",International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 – 8887), Volume 134 – No.16, January 2016
- [14] F Delicato, P Pires, T Batista, Resource Management for Internet of Things, "SPRINGER BRIEFS IN COMPUTER SCIENCE".
- [15] "Introduction to the Architectural Reference Model for the Internet of Things"